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Implementation and Challenges of the K-12 Program in Secondary Schools of District VI Quezon City: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

This research aimed to determine the level of implementation, and challenges of K-12 program in public secondary schools of District VI, Quezon City, to serve as a basis for an action plan. The study used the descriptive survey method of research. It used a survey questionnaire in a checklist form to gather the data from two groups of respondents: the teachers, and the school leaders/ coordinators. Based on the findings, it was found out that the level of implementation of the K-12 program was high in terms of instructional materials, school facilities and equipment, and teachers' preparedness as assessed by the two groups of respondents. In addition, there was a significant difference between the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of K-12 implementation in terms of instructional materials, but no significant difference in terms of school facilities and equipment, and teachers' preparedness. Moreso, the challenges encountered by the teachers with regard to the K-12 program implementation were a) congested most essential learning competencies, b) time allotment is not enough, c) lack of additional training, d) the student-teacher ratio is not proportional and, e) facilities are lacking like advanced laboratories for experiments. On the other hand, the group of school leaders/ coordinators encountered challenges as follows; a) lack of technology-based equipment for advanced subjects, b) insufficient number of training days, and c) time allotment is not enough to cover all the lessons.

Keywords: *K-12 program, implementation, challenges, action plan*

Introduction

Education is important for improving students' lives as well as the society as a whole. The education system in the Philippines needs to be aware of the crucial steps to take in order to produce graduates who are not just focused on self-improvement but also mindful of the demands of society. An essential part of encouraging growth is having citizens who are responsive and productive. The Philippine educational system now has new organizational structures because of this K-12 curriculum.

The senior high school provides specialties with a variety of tracks and strands. As stated in the paper published by Hamdan-Mansour (2021), once students graduate from senior high school, it will be simpler for them to adapt to new situations. Students would have two more years to think things over. If the student decides to pursue higher education, this will be a tool to gauge his or her interest in the preferred college course.

In an article written by Garcia (2020), she stated that to guarantee that K-12 graduates will be considered for employment, the DepEd has also entered into agreements with business associations, chambers of commerce, and industry players. Along with a greater emphasis on college readiness standards, a system of competency requirements is being put in place to match the abilities of the workforce to those required by businesses.

In the Philippine setting, Poblador (2022) entails in her paper that K-12 implementation, specifically in grades 11 and 12, plays an important role if the student after graduation intends to pursue jobs in countries where companies require a minimum of 16 years of formal education to qualify for employment.

As cited by Dizon (2019), one of the conflicts that this program faces are teacher preparedness. In addition, a study published by Barbour (2019) stated that there was a great need for schools to improve their physical facilities and educational resources to implement the K-12 program effectively and efficiently. Another local study published by Vizconde (2019) elaborates that K-12 implementation needs sufficient resources for its implementation.

In this regard, the researcher included the categories of instructional materials, school facilities and equipment, and teachers' preparedness in this study to see if this was also a prevailing concern in secondary schools in District VI of Quezon City in their implementation of the K-12 program. With the results of this research, officials would be able to know the status of implementation and the challenges that the aforesaid institution was facing, along with the action plan that could be taken to provide the best education for its enrollees.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the level of implementation, and challenges of K-12 program in public secondary schools of District VI, Quezon City, to serve as a basis for an action plan. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of the K-12 program in terms of the following variables as assessed by the teachers and the school leaders /coordinators?

- 1.1. Instructional Materials
- 1.2. School Facilities and Equipment
- 1.3. Teachers' Preparedness
2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of implementation of the K-12 program in terms of the aforementioned variables?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the two groups of respondents in the implementation of the K-12 program?
4. Based on the result of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Literature Review

The SHS curriculum, which was introduced in 2016, seeks to generate graduates who are fully developed, equipped with 21st-century abilities, and ready for the future, regardless of their chosen paths, whether it be higher education, obtaining middle-level skills, employment, or entrepreneurship (Narcoda, 2018).

DepEd is putting the SHS and SHS Modeling into practice to ease the transition from the current 10-year basic education to a 12-year program. The K–12 curriculum is competency-based and standardized. It is all-inclusive and designed with the community's and learners' needs in mind. The K–12 program was meticulously researched and developed based on findings from other nations' research as well as domestic achievements and failures in education. One can access the curriculum on the DepEd website. The full curriculum has never before been digitized and made available to the general public (Estacio, 2019).

In addition, Rice and Ortiz (2021) emphasized how crucial it is to have access to instructional materials in order to achieve effectiveness in delivering lectures and supervision in the school system. Abubakar (2020) cited the apparent shortage of instructional materials and their underutilization that are necessary to boost the abilities of dominating organs and make up for the deficiencies of sense organs. He stated that in order to support their teachings, educators should make every effort to provide locally produced instructional materials in place of standard ones given by the national government.

According to Mercado (2019), teaching entails having the entire capacity and necessary teacher preparedness to deliver the student's knowledge and abilities in a particular field of study specifically the K-12 curriculum.

Teachers must be included in decision-making by leaders (Keating, 2020). A school administrator should make sure that the school system is implemented smoothly and steadily by hiring qualified teachers and department heads, regularly checking the workload of the staff, and making the necessary adjustments when things go wrong on according to plan (Elbanna, 2019). The reasons stated above affirm the researchers' objective to include the perspective of school administrators in implementing the senior high school K-12 program.

A research paper penned by Tabora (2020) elaborates that instructional materials have been observed as a powerful strategy to bring about effective teaching and learning. The importance of quality and adequate instructional materials in teaching and learning can occur through their effective utilization during classroom teaching. Another study conducted by Tety (2019) added that instructional materials here include all the tools that teachers can use to make learning more interesting and memorable. instructional materials include books, audio-visual, software, and hardware of educational technology.

Relatively, Mendiola and Estonanto (2022) published in their research the resourcefulness of teachers and presented the importance to explore local sources for essential instructional materials to complement or substitute standard ones. They emphasized the significance of improvising instructional materials to create tangible and authentic learning experiences, involving students in material production, being cost-effective, and prioritizing teacher-student resources.

Furthermore, A study conducted in the Philippines by Ford (2019) entails that understanding how specific resources provided in learning spaces contribute to the physical learning environment is crucial. The author added that educational resources, such as teaching materials, technical equipment, and student materials, have been found to correlate with the quality and condition of school facilities.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research. The researcher did not manipulate any variables but utilized statistical analysis and described the relationship between or among variables with the raw data gathered from the respondents. Descriptive research is a form of non-experimental research methodology that employs statistical analysis to investigate the link between or among variables (McNabb, 2020).

Respondents

The respondents used in the study served as the main source of data. They were taken from the nine public secondary schools in District VI, Division of Quezon City. There was a total of 280 teachers and 39 school leaders and coordinators involved in the study. The biggest number of respondents came from New Era High School, followed by Tandang Sora National High School. On the other hand, the lowest number of respondents came from Talipapa Senior High School. The teacher respondents were selected through purposive

sampling while the school leaders and coordinators were chosen through census survey.

Instrument

The main research instrument used in this the researcher drafted an assessment survey- questionnaire that was validated by the experts and underwent a reliability test. The developed questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part I- contained questions to determine the level of implementation of the K-12 program and Part II- consisted of questions to determine the challenges encountered in the implementation of the K-12 program.

Procedure

A preliminary interview was done by the researcher to know the statements that were included in the finalized assessment tool. This served as a guide to the researcher as to which variables to include in the survey tool and to what variables the assessment tool should focus on. Letters to conduct the preliminary interview were secured and signed by the principal of New Era High School. An approval letter from the Division of Quezon City DepEd was also secured. After the finalization and approval was received by the researcher to conduct the data gathering procedure, she then secured another permit from the principals of the schools to conduct a data gathering for the current study. The researcher communicated to the respondents personally to explain her study and hand over their informed consent. Since the researcher was considering the institutional protocol, she then explained the details of the study, including the objectives, benefits, and risks, if any. Once the respondents affirmed that they wanted to be part of the study, the researcher collected the informed consent and asked the respondents to affix their signatures below the paper.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher strictly adhered to ethical considerations as this study involves people as respondents. Respect for the dignity of research participants was prioritized by keeping the respondents' identities anonymous. Full consent was obtained from the participants prior to the study. The researcher provided the participants with a consent form that stated the willingness of the participants to join the study, details about the study, and how their responses would be stored. Along with the consent form was a specific explanation of the study including the risks, benefits, and new the normal adaptation. Researchers secured the participant's signature affixed to the provided consent.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Level of Implementation of the K-12 Program

Table 1. *Level of Implementation of the K-12 Program in terms of Instructional Materials*

Instructional Materials	Teachers		School Leaders and coordinators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. There are modules online and other e-learning materials for K- 12 subject areas, for learners to utilize in their study.	4.10	H	4.36	VH
2. There are printed materials such as journals, magazines, and books per subject area for the study of learners.	3.49	H	3.85	H
3. There are supplementary reading materials about K-12 for review of students on exams.	3.59	H	3.51	H
4. There are audio-visual materials about the K-12 curriculum for students and educators to use.	3.63	H	3.62	H
5. The school provides other materials, such as laboratory instructional books and papers, computer laboratory sheets and instructional materials, and reading materials for practical competencies that entail student learning.	3.48	H	3.72	H
6. The instructional materials provided by the school are up to date for teachers to use.	3.53	H	3.67	H
7. Books, journals, and magazines provided by the school are utilized for students' improvement in learning.	3.45	H	3.62	H
8. Instructional materials provided by the school cover the track/strand of the class.	3.54	H	3.59	H
Average Weighted Mean:	3.60	H	3.74	H

Legend: WM-Weighted mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation, 4.20-5.00 (VH) Very High, 3.40-4.19 (H) High, 2.60-3.39 (M) Moderate, 1.80-2.59 (L) Low, 1.00-1.79 (VL) Very Low

The level of implementation of the K-12 Program in terms of instructional materials was assessed by the teacher respondents and school leaders/ coordinators as high with an average weighted mean of 3.60 and 3.74, respectively. The teachers, school leaders, and coordinators believed that the instructional materials for K-12 program are adequate for the students to utilize. For every subject, printed materials such as books, journals, and periodicals are also available. A paper published by Tabora (2020) stated that instructional

materials are a powerful strategy to bring about effective teaching and learning. The importance of quality and adequate instructional materials in teaching and learning can occur through their effective utilization during classroom teaching.

Table 2. *Level of Implementation of the K-12 Program in terms of School Facilities and Equipment*

School Facilities and Equipment	Teachers		School Leaders and coordinators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The school has ventilation that accommodates the teaching and learning processes.	3.89	H	4.33	VH
2. Classrooms have chairs, tables, and other equipment needed to facilitate learning.	4.07	H	4.26	VH
3. The school has laboratories/facilities for skills training.	3.74	H	3.46	H
4. The school has a multi-purpose hall (for meetings, conferences, and other gatherings).	4.15	H	4.08	H
5. The school hires school guards and maintenance personnel that accommodate the needs of the students and educators.	4.44	VH	4.41	VH
6. Inspection of the school buildings is done in preparation for calamities (fire, earthquake, flood).	4.18	H	4.33	VH
7. There are buildings designated for classes of educators in various subject areas.	3.95	H	4.08	H
8. There are materials/equipment for classes that require laboratories or skills training.	3.64	H	3.23	H
Average Weighted Mean:	4.01	H	4.02	H

Legend: WM-Weighted mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation, 4.20-5.00 (VH) Very High, 3.40-4.19 (H) High, 2.60-3.39 (M) Moderate, 1.80-2.59 (L) Low, 1.00-1.79 (VL) Very Low

The finding implies that the teachers, school leaders, and coordinators believed that the school facilities and equipment for the K-12 program are adequate for the students to utilize. Both teachers and school heads perceived that the institution they are working for provides ventilation suitable for teaching and learning activities. Classroom furniture and equipment necessary for facilitating learning are available. Certain buildings are set aside for use by instructors teaching various subject areas. This is a good indicator of the provision of quality education as supported by some studies. A research that strengthens the data presented in the table was the study of Fearnley and Malay (2022) in Manila, Philippines, in which the researcher investigated how classroom setup affected student participation in the class and discovered that flexible seating arrangements and natural lighting were linked to better student behavior and academic achievement

Table 3. *Level of Implementation of the K-12 Program in terms of Teachers' Preparedness*

Teachers' Preparedness	Teachers		School Leaders and coordinators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. There are numerous trainings for educators in teaching K-12.	4.00	H	4.10	H
2. Teachers meet the standards to implement the K-12 program (teachers have training certificates, units on a master's degree, or a degree from a master's program or higher).	4.13	H	4.13	H
3. School heads/ school administrators provide teachers support in the form of seminars, meetings, and various ways of communication among teachers on implementing the K-12 program.	4.20	VH	4.26	VH
4. Teachers have training/seminars on the K-12 program.	4.16	H	4.41	VH
5. Teachers have technical training to cope with global competitiveness.	4.08	H	4.03	H
6. Adequate time for seminars is given to the teachers to prepare for the subject area that they will teach.	3.95	H	3.95	H
7. There are educators for skill-based classes (ex. TLE, Science laboratories, and others).	4.15	H	3.97	H
8. Teachers receive support (allocation of budget for activities, allotment of calendar time for events, appropriate student-teacher ratio) from the school administration for their preparedness in teaching at senior high school.	3.75	H	3.49	H
Average Weighted Mean:	4.05	H	4.04	H

Legend: WM-Weighted mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation, 4.20-5.00 (VH) Very High, 3.40-4.19 (H) High, 2.60-3.39 (M) Moderate, 1.80-2.59 (L) Low, 1.00-1.79 (VL) Very Low

The table reflects the level of implementation of the K-12 Program in terms of teachers' preparedness which was assessed by the teacher respondents as high with an average weighted mean of 4.05 and likewise the school leaders and coordinators with an average weighted mean of 4.04.

The findings implies that teachers, school leaders, and coordinators believed that teacher preparedness is at high level. Both the teachers and school heads perceived that the institution they are working fulfill the prerequisites to carry out the K-12 program. Teachers can choose from several K-12 teachers' training programs. For the implementation of K-12 programs, school leaders and coordinators provide support to teachers through conferences, seminars, and other forms of communication.

This was strengthened by the article of Chua (2020) about the Philippine implementation of K-12 which elaborates that there is a lot of room for improvement in terms of readiness to implement K-12. This is evident with the curriculum, which calls for enhancement and more funding to cover the basic inputs such as provision for an appropriate number of teachers and educators' preparedness.

Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the implementation of the K-12 program

Table 4. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the K-12 Program Implementation in terms of Instructional Materials*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teacher respondents	3.60	0.02	Reject H ₀	Significant
School leaders and coordinators' respondents	3.74			

The data reveal that the teacher respondents and school leaders and coordinators' respondents have different perspectives on the implementation of the K-12 program in terms of instructional materials. This was affirmed by the study of Tichenor (2020) which stated that it is common for administrators and teachers to view the distribution of educational resources to children from different angles.

Table 5. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the K-12 Program Implementation in terms of School Facilities and Equipment*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teacher respondents	4.01	0.82	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
School leaders and coordinators' respondents	4.02			

The data reveal that both the teacher respondents, and school leaders and coordinators' respondents have the same perceptions of the implementation of the K-12 program in terms of school facilities and equipment. This was strengthened by the study of Boyers (2019) which stated that there is a shared understanding between educators and administrators regarding the provision of resources and amenities for pupils.

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the K-12 Program Implementation in terms of Teachers' Preparedness*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teacher respondents	4.05	0.98	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
School leaders and coordinators' respondents	4.04			

The data reveal that the teacher respondents, and school leaders and coordinators' respondents have the same perceptions of the implementation of the K-12 program in terms of teachers' preparedness. The deduced analysis mentioned was affirmed by the article of Tantawy (2020) which stated that administrators and teachers both agree that giving educators access to seminars and training opportunities is crucial.

Challenges Encountered by the Two Groups of Respondents in the Implementation of the K-12 program

The challenges encountered by the teachers with regard to the K-12 program implementation were: a) congested most essential learning competencies, b) time allotment is not enough, c) lack of additional training, d) the student-teacher ratio is not proportional and, e) facilities are lacking like advanced laboratories for experiments. On the other hand, the group of school leaders/ coordinators encountered challenges as follows; a) lack of technology-based equipment for advanced subjects, b) insufficient number of training days, and c) time allotment is not enough to cover all the lessons.

Action Plan for Enhancement of K-12 Program Implementation

Rationale

Determining the K-12 program's implementation level aids in assessing how well it accomplishes its objectives. Insights into areas of success and parts in need of development can be gained from this assessment, enabling focused initiatives to raise educational standards. Determining the level of implementation of the K-12 program and the challenges faced by the teachers and school leaders/ coordinators will serve as guide on how the K-12 program implementation will succeed. It is of paramount importance to receive support from the leaders of the institution where the result of this study can be taken into consideration in drafting an action plan. This is to acknowledge

that there is room for improvement in the implementation of K-12 programs to uplift the quality of education the learners ought to receive and unload some challenges that teachers are experiencing.

It was disclosed in this study that there were challenges encountered by the teachers with regard to the K-12 program implementation and these were: a) congested most essential learning competencies, b) time allotment is not enough, c) lack of additional training, d) the student-teacher ratio is not proportional and, e) facilities are lacking like advanced laboratories for experiments. On the other hand, the group of school leaders/ coordinators encountered challenges as follows; a) lack of technology-based equipment for advanced subjects, b) insufficient number of training days, and c) time allotment is not enough to cover all the lessons.

In view of the foregoing challenges, an action plan was proposed in this study to hopefully address the problems that affect the implementation of the K-12 program.

Objectives

The proposed action plan, based on the result of the current study aims to attain the following specific objectives:

To enlighten the officials about the steps that could be taken to improve the provision of quality education under the K-12 program.

To guide the school administrators on what strategies are needed to improve the status of the K-12 program.

To align the goals of a school institution with the improvement needed for the K-12 curriculum.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The subject institutions provide adequate instructional materials, school equipment, well-ventilated school facilities that accommodate learning, and adequate support to its personnel for teacher preparedness.

There exists a notable distinction between the perspectives of teachers and school leaders/coordinators regarding the K-12 program implementation in terms of instructional materials. Conversely, the school facilities and equipment, and teacher preparedness have congruence in viewpoints between teachers and school leaders/coordinators regarding the implementation level of the K-12 program in terms of school facilities and equipment, and teacher preparedness.

There are challenges encountered by both teachers and school leaders/coordinators in the implementation of the K-12 program, thus, there is a need for comprehensive support and collaboration within the education system.

Addressing the challenges presented in this research, requires a concerted effort from policymakers, administrators, educators, and other stakeholders to ensure the successful implementation of K-12 program and, ultimately, to provide students with the quality education they deserve.

References

- Abubakar, M. (2020). Impact of instructional materials on students' academic performance in Physics, in Sokoto-Nigeria. ResearchGate, 141.
- Boyers, N. (2019). Teacher and Administrator Perspective of Project-Based Learning Teacher and Administrator Perspective of Project-Based Learning. 125.
- Chua, D. (2020). IMPACT STATEMENTS ON THE K-12 SCIENCE PROGRAM IN THE ENHANCED BASIC EDUCATION CURRICULUM IN PROVINCIAL SCHOOLS. 77.
- Elbanna, A. (2019). Skolera. Retrieved from <https://blog.skolera.com/role-of-administrator-in-school/>.
- Estacio, M. P. (2019, September 2). Department of Education. Retrieved from [https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/09/02/all-set-for-k-to-12-implementation/#:~:text=K%20to%2012%20Milestone&text=In%20School%20Year%202012%2D2013,law%](https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/09/02/all-set-for-k-to-12-implementation/#:~:text=K%20to%2012%20Milestone&text=In%20School%20Year%202012%2D2013,law%20).
- Ford, A. (2019). PLANNING SCIENCE CLASSROOM FACILITIES AND RESOURCES TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' ATTITUDES. 92.
- Garcia, E. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.epi.org/publication/the-consequences-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-for-education-performance-and-equity-in-the-united-states-what-can-we-learn-from-pre-pandemic-research-to-inform-relief-recovery-and-rebuilding/>.
- Hamdan-Mansour, A. (2021). Prediction of Anxiety among Senior High School Students. ResearchGate, 112. Retrieved from <https://learninglinks.edu.ph/blog/how-senior-highschool-prepares-your-child-for-the-future/>.
- Keating, K. (2020, September 6). Retrieved from <http://www.sciepub.com/reference/97619>.
- Malay, C., & Fearnley, M. (2022). Factors Affecting Student Satisfaction, Perceived Learning and Academic Performance in an

Emergency Online Science Course. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 117

McNabb, D. (2020, March 22). Descriptive Research. In D. McNabb, *Research Methods for Political Science: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Method Approaches*. Maryland: Routledge.

Mendiola, A., & Estonanto, A. (2022). Utilization of Instructional Materials Developed by the Mathematics Teachers in the Province of Sorsogon, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Education and e-learning*, 131.

Mercado, R. (2019). Teaching Preparedness and Outcomes of the Teacher Education Programs to the Graduates. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 125.

Narcoda, S. H. (2018). K-12 Curriculum Implementation: Phenomenological Study. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY*, 98.

Poblador, S. A. (2022). K-12 Transition in Action: Threading the opportunities and challenges on the implementation of senior high school. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/projects/48284-001/main>

Rice, M., & Ortiz, K. (2021). Evaluating Digital Instructional Materials for K-12 Online and Blended Learning. *PubMed*, 133.

Tabora, J. (2020). Challenges in Implementing K-12 and Transformative Education. *ResearchGate*, 79.

Tantawy, N. (2020). Investigating Teachers' Perceptions of the Influence of Professional Development on Teachers' Performance and Career Progression. *Arab World English Journal*, 132.

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